

Failure Modes and Remediations in LLM-Driven Automated Machine Learning: A Case Study on Network Intrusion Detection

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Abstract

I present an empirical study of an LLM-driven automated machine learning (AutoML) loop applied to binary network intrusion detection on the CICIDS-2017 dataset. The framework adapts Karpathy’s autoresearch concept to tabular classification: Claude Sonnet 4.6 iteratively rewrites a detector script, which is executed as a subprocess and evaluated against held-out validation and test sets. Over four sessions and 27 runs, I document six distinct failure modes: revert-loop stagnation, unsupervised feature engineering causing train/test distribution mismatch, resource budget violations, platform encoding crashes, deprecated API incompatibilities, and cross-process pickle scope errors. Concrete remediations are provided for each. My best model achieves weighted F1 = 0.9992 on CICIDS-2017, consistent with published benchmarks. The central finding is that near a performance ceiling, the primary challenge of LLM-driven AutoML is not model quality but *system reliability*: ensuring the agent explores meaningfully, respects execution constraints, and produces evaluable outputs. I provide a reusable, dataset-agnostic framework and a reproducible failure taxonomy intended to be useful to practitioners building similar systems.

CCS Concepts

• **Security and privacy** → **Intrusion detection systems**; • **Computing methodologies** → *Machine learning*; • **Human-centered computing** → Empirical studies in HCI.

Keywords

LLM agents, AutoML, network intrusion detection, CICIDS-2017, failure taxonomy, automated machine learning research

1 Introduction

Using large language models (LLMs) to automate machine learning research has attracted increasing interest in recent years. The general approach, demonstrated by Karpathy in the context of LLM training [1] and extended by others toward broader scientific automation [2, 3], is to place an LLM in a closed feedback loop: it generates code, the code runs, the results come back, and the LLM tries again. The appeal is that this delegates hyperparameter tuning, architecture search, and model selection to the model itself.

Network intrusion detection is a natural domain for evaluating such systems. The CICIDS-2017 benchmark [4], which contains approximately 2.8M labeled network flow records across 78 raw features, is large enough to expose runtime constraints, imbalanced enough to require careful class weighting, and well-studied enough that published baselines provide a point of comparison.

I built and operated such a loop over four experimental sessions totaling 27 agent iterations. Code generation used Claude Sonnet 4.6; a separate Claude Haiku 4.5 instance summarized the experiment ledger after each run to keep history manageable within the context window. Rather than reporting a new performance result, my best weighted F1 of 0.9992 is consistent with the well-documented ceiling for tree ensemble methods on this dataset, I focus on what went wrong during those 27 iterations and how each problem was fixed.

Six classes of failure emerged across the four sessions: (1) revert-loop stagnation, in which the agent repeatedly regenerates identical code; (2) autonomous feature engineering that creates a silent train/test distribution mismatch; (3) resource budget violations from computationally expensive operations; (4) platform encoding crashes caused by non-ASCII characters in log output; (5) API incompatibilities arising from the gap between the LLM’s training data and the deployed Python and library versions; and (6) cross-process pickle scope errors caused by serializing custom class instances. Each failure was reproduced across multiple runs and resolved through targeted changes to the orchestration layer or the system prompt.

The progression across sessions is measurable: 2 evaluable runs out of 10 in Session 1, 5 out of 5 with zero timeouts but a systematic val/test gap in Session 2, 3 out of 5 with the gap eliminated in Session 3, and 4 out of 7 with confirmed test F1 in Session 4. The improvements came from the remediations, not from the model.

I make three contributions. First, an empirical failure taxonomy for LLM-driven AutoML loops, with root cause analysis and reproducible remediations for six failure classes. Second, a dataset-agnostic open-source framework that introspects dataset statistics at startup and injects them into the agent prompt dynamically. Third, an analysis of how performance ceiling effects constrain the usefulness of the improvement signal in agentic research loops.

2 Related Work

2.1 LLM-Driven AutoML

Recent work has explored LLMs as orchestrators of the full AutoML pipeline. Liu et al. [2] describe a structured multi-agent framework for scientific research automation. Huang and Tao [5] apply an LLM-based AutoML agent to multimodal data management tasks. These systems generally operate under controlled or idealized conditions. The present work contributes empirical failure data from an extended operational deployment on a real, large-scale dataset under realistic time and compute constraints.

Figure 1: System component architecture. The fixed components (evaluate.py, git) are never modified by the agent.

2.2 Network Intrusion Detection on CICIDS-2017

CICIDS-2017 [4] is among the most widely evaluated benchmarks for network anomaly detection. Arshad et al. [6] survey machine learning approaches on this dataset and consistently find that tree ensemble methods, including Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, and ExtraTrees, achieve weighted F1 above 0.999 in binary classification mode. My results are consistent with these baselines, confirming that the dataset presents a performance ceiling for tree-based methods. Jose and Jose [7] report similar findings for deep neural networks, noting longer training times without commensurate improvement in F1.

2.3 Reliability of LLM Agents

Vinay [8] provides a system-level taxonomy of LLM failure modes across deployment contexts. Ashrafi et al. [9] evaluate multi-agent code generation reliability. The present work is complementary in that it characterizes failures specific to the closed feedback loop structure of an AutoML agent. In particular, the revert-loop stagnation pattern (Section 6.1) arises from the interaction between the improvement criterion and the prompt construction mechanism, which is not addressed in prior taxonomies.

3 System Architecture

The system follows a closed-loop structure (Figure 1). An orchestrator (agent.py) calls an LLM to generate a detector script, executes it as a subprocess, evaluates the result against a held-out test set, and iterates. Four components interact in each iteration.

3.1 Orchestrator (agent.py)

The orchestrator manages all persistent state: the improvement ledger, the current best detector, the last-attempted detector (Section 6.1), and the dataset statistics block. At startup, it reads train.csv in 100k-row chunks to compute the actual dataset dimensions, including row count, feature count, class distribution, imbalance ratio,

and scaled runtime estimates. These are injected as a dataset context block prepended to the system prompt before every Sonnet call.

3.2 Code Generator (Claude Sonnet 4.6)

Each iteration provides the model with a system prompt consisting of the dataset context and static guidance, followed by a user message containing: (a) the current best detector.py, (b) the last-attempted-but-reverted detector.py if it differs from the current best, (c) the Haiku ledger summary, and (d) the last run result as JSON. The model returns a complete new detector.py. A validation step checks for required CLI arguments and output markers before execution.

3.3 Ledger Summarizer (Claude Haiku 4.5)

After each run, Claude Haiku 4.5 summarizes the experiment ledger into a block of at most 400 tokens, identifying the best result to date, observed failure patterns, and model families not yet attempted. This summary is included in the next Sonnet call to provide compressed history without exhausting the context window.

3.4 Fixed Evaluator (evaluate.py)

A separate fixed script loads the saved model file, either an sklearn.pkl bundle or a PyTorch.pt checkpoint, and runs inference on the held-out test set. It prints a final JSON line containing weighted F1 and AUROC. The agent is instructed never to modify this file. Separating agent-controlled validation on val.csv from fixed evaluation on test.csv provides a tamper-proof measure of generalization.

4 Experimental Setup

4.1 Dataset

CICIDS-2017 [4] was processed into a binary classification task (normal = 0, any attack = 1) with an 80/10/10 train/val/test split: 1,979,513 training rows, 424,181 validation rows, and 424,182 test rows, all with 70 numeric flow-level features. Class imbalance is approximately 4:1 (normal to anomaly). The label column name is loaded dynamically from a metadata.json file; no column names are hardcoded in any component.

4.2 Hardware and Models

All experiments ran on a consumer CPU (Windows 11, Intel Core i9-10900K, no GPU). The per-run training budget was 300 seconds, with a hard 360-second kill limit enforced by the orchestrator. Code generation used claude-sonnet-4-6 at \$3/\$15 per million input/output tokens. Ledger summarization used claude-haiku-4-5-20251001 at \$1/\$5 per million input/output tokens.

4.3 Session Protocol

Four sessions were conducted sequentially. Prompt and orchestrator changes were applied between sessions as remediations were developed. Session 1 ran 10 iterations using the initial configuration. Sessions 2, 3, and 4 ran 5, 5, and 7 iterations respectively, each incorporating the remediations described in Section 6. The framework

Figure 2: Val F1 vs. Test F1 across Sessions 2 and 3. The gap in Session 2, as large as 0.122 F1 points in run 1, is attributable entirely to LLM-generated feature engineering that is absent from the fixed test harness. Prohibiting feature engineering in the system prompt eliminates the gap in Session 3.

was generalized to support arbitrary labeled tabular datasets prior to Session 4.

5 Results

Table 1 summarizes all 27 runs across four sessions. The best model across all sessions, an HGB + RF + ExtraTrees soft-voting ensemble with CalibratedClassifierCV, achieved val F1 = 0.9992 and test F1 = 0.9991, consistent with published benchmarks for tree ensemble methods on CICIDS-2017.

Session 1 (10 runs) was dominated by stagnation. Runs 2 through 7 produced byte-for-byte identical code, varying in val F1 by ± 0.0002 due to thread-scheduling non-determinism in RandomForest with `n_jobs=-1`. Two timeout failures also occurred. Session 2 (5 runs) eliminated timeouts through timing-probe guidance but introduced a systematic val/test gap from autonomous feature engineering, with a worst-case gap of 0.122 F1 points in run 1. Session 3 (5 runs) eliminated the gap entirely but exposed two new failure modes: a deprecated sklearn API (run 2) and a model serialization incompatibility involving PyTorch (run 4). Figure 2 illustrates the val/test gap pattern across Sessions 2 and 3.

Session 4 (7 runs) demonstrated the cumulative effect of the prior remediations. Four of six completed runs produced confirmed test F1 values with no val/test gap, and no stagnation occurred. Two new failures appeared: run 0 encountered the cross-process pickle scope error described in Section 6.6, and run 1 failed due to an execution error of unknown origin with a runtime of 81.4 seconds. Run 5 reproduced FM-3 when the agent attempted a hybrid HGB and PyTorch MLP architecture. The MLP reached epoch 10 with 313 seconds elapsed and val F1 = 0.973, still below ensemble performance, and was killed at the 360-second limit. The FM-6 remediation applied between runs 0 and 2 of Session 4 held for all subsequent runs in that session.

6 Failure Taxonomy

Six distinct failure classes were observed across the four sessions. Figure 3 shows their distribution by session.

6.1 FM-1: Revert-Loop Stagnation

Root cause. The improvement criterion reverts `detector.py` to the best-scoring version when a run fails to improve. The next

Figure 3: Run outcome distribution by session. Annotations indicate the session boundary at which each major remediation was applied.

Sonnet call therefore starts from the same input as the previous one and, absent other information, produces the same output. With XGBoost excluded from the system prompt, Sonnet generated the same HGB-for-XGB substitution eight consecutive times in Session 1. Non-determinism in RandomForest with `n_jobs=-1` produced val F1 variation of ± 0.0002 across functionally identical code, occasionally triggering false improvement signals and resetting the baseline.

Remediation. Before any revert, the newly generated code is written to `last_attempted_detector.py`. The next iteration injects this file alongside the current best detector, with an explicit note that it was reverted and must not be regenerated. This breaks the prompt-input cycle while preserving the revert-to-best logic. Session 2 showed genuine architectural diversity across all five runs following this change.

6.2 FM-2: Feature Engineering Distribution Mismatch

Root cause. Without explicit constraint, Sonnet created 58–67 engineered features per run in Session 2, including log transforms, packet ratios, and flow-rate interactions. These were applied identically to the training and validation splits, so validation scores appeared normal. The fixed `evaluate.py` harness receives only raw features from `test.csv`. Missing engineered columns are filled with zeros by default, corrupting test-set inference. The worst-case gap was 0.122 F1 points in run 1 of Session 2, where class-1 recall collapsed from 0.999 on validation to 0.46 on test due to threshold miscalibration on the shifted probability distribution.

Remediation. Feature engineering is prohibited in the system prompt. The prohibition includes an explicit explanation of the failure mechanism, specifically that engineered features will be silently zeroed out at test time, rather than only the instruction itself. Providing the causal mechanism reduces the likelihood that the model will generate workarounds that satisfy the letter but not the intent of the constraint. Session 3 confirmed complete elimination of the gap across all five runs.

6.3 FM-3: Resource Budget Violations

Root cause. Two timeout patterns were observed. In the first, a three-model ensemble completed training in 263 seconds but entered threshold optimization with 17 seconds remaining and exceeded the 360-second kill limit. In the second, a StackingClassifier with 3-fold cross-validation on 2M rows multiplied training

Table 1: All 27 runs across four sessions. *Gap* denotes a val/test F1 discrepancy caused by feature engineering applied during training but absent from the fixed test harness.

Run	Session	Approach	Val F1	Test F1	Status	Runtime
0	S1	XGBoost + RF Ensemble	0.9992	0.9991	✓ Best	167.5 s
1	S1	HGB + RF + ET (3-model)	–	–	Timeout	360 s
2–7	S1	HGB + RF (identical ×6)	0.9988–0.9992	0.9989–0.9992	Stagnation	31–251 s
8	S1	HGB + RF	0.9993	0.9989	✓ Best	241.5 s
9	S1	HGB + Stacking (3-fold CV)	–	–	Timeout	360 s
0	S2	ET + HGB soft-vote	0.9991	0.9988	✓ Best	~120 s
1	S2	ET + HGB + RF (eng. features)	0.9991	0.8775	Gap	181.7 s
2	S2	ET + HGB (l_2 -reg = 0.1)	0.9991	0.9529	Gap	~130 s
3	S2	RF + HGB soft-vote	0.9992	0.9585	Gap	122.2 s
4	S2	ET + HGB (n -est = 120)	0.9991	0.9616	Gap	~140 s
0	S3	HGB + ET (raw features)	0.9991	0.9991	✓ Best	117.7 s
1	S3	HGB + RF + ET + CalibratedCV	0.9992	0.9991	✓ Best	189.8 s
2	S3	Stacking + LogReg meta	0.0	–	API Error (FM-5)	53.0 s
3	S3	HGB + RF + ET (repeat)	0.9992	0.9991	No improvement	183.4 s
4	S3	PyTorch MLP (70→512→256→128)	0.9754	–	Eval Fail (FM-5)	221.4 s
0	S4	Custom SoftVotingEnsemble class	0.9992	–	Eval Fail (FM-6)	183.8 s
1	S4	Custom ensemble (unknown error)	–	–	Failed	81.4 s
2	S4	HGB + ET + RF + HGB2 (4-model)	0.9992	0.9991	✓	193.7 s
3	S4	HGB + ET + HGB2 + RF (weighted)	0.9992	0.9991	✓	202.2 s
4	S4	HGB + ET + HGB2 + RF + HGB3 (5-model)	0.9992	0.9991	✓	230.1 s
5	S4	HGB + PyTorch MLP (70→256→128→64)	–	–	Timeout (FM-3)	360.1 s
6	S4	HGB + ET + RF + HGB2 (4-model)	0.9992	0.9991	✓	186.7 s

time by a factor of three, making timeout unavoidable regardless of individual model speed. A third instance occurred in Session 4 run 5, where the agent combined HGB with a PyTorch MLP. The MLP was still training at epoch 10 with 313 seconds elapsed, below ensemble performance at F1 = 0.973, and was killed at the 360-second limit. This recurrence illustrates a structural limitation of the timing-probe approach: the probe extrapolates from subsample training time, which is informative for ensemble methods with roughly constant per-sample cost but does not predict the number of epochs required for neural network convergence on a given dataset.

Remediation. The system prompt was updated with empirically measured per-algorithm runtimes on this hardware, scaled dynamically from actual dataset dimensions at startup. A mandatory timing-probe pattern using a 10% subsample with linear extrapolation was added as executable code. Full-dataset cross-validation was explicitly prohibited. These changes eliminated timeouts in Sessions 2 and 3. The Session 4 recurrence for the neural architecture suggests that deep learning approaches may require a separate budget heuristic based on epoch time rather than sample time.

6.4 FM-4: Platform Encoding Crash

Root cause. Sonnet included a Unicode arrow character (U+2192, →) in a log statement. Windows defaults to cp1252 for stdout encoding, which cannot represent this character. The subprocess crashed before any training occurred.

Remediation. Two changes were applied. First, agent.py sets PYTHONIOENCODING=utf-8 in the subprocess environment and specifies encoding="utf-8" on the Popen call, providing a runtime

guarantee independent of whatever the generated code does. Second, the system prompt adds an explicit instruction to use only ASCII characters in all print and log statements.

6.5 FM-5: Deprecated API Incompatibilities

Root cause. Two incompatibilities with the Python 3.14 runtime environment were observed. First, LogisticRegression(`multi_class=...`) raises `TypeError` because the `multi_class` parameter was removed in Python 3.14 following deprecation in sklearn 1.3. The model’s training data contains valid uses of this parameter, so it continues to generate code that fails at runtime. Second, `joblib.dump()` cannot serialize PyTorch tensors: Python 3.14’s pickle module raises `UnpicklingError` when it encounters PyTorch’s non-ASCII persistent IDs, crashing the evaluator even when the detector script itself completed successfully.

Remediation. A section titled “Known broken APIs” was added to the system prompt, listing each incompatibility with the exact error message produced and the correct alternative. For PyTorch, detectors are required to save the model state dict to a .pt file and write a `model_config.json` with architecture parameters; the orchestrator falls back to the .pt file if no .pk1 is found. This class of failure will recur as runtime environments evolve; the broken-API list requires ongoing maintenance as a result.

6.6 FM-6: Cross-Process Pickle Scope Error

Root cause. In Session 4 run 0, the model defined a custom sklearn subclass named `SoftVotingEnsemble` that extended `BaseEstimator` and `ClassifierMixin`, then serialized an instance of it with

`joblib.dump()`. Python’s pickle protocol records the class location as `__main__.SoftVotingEnsemble`. When `evaluate.py` subsequently called `joblib.load()`, pickle attempted to locate `SoftVotingEnsemble` in `evaluate.py`’s `__main__` module, which contains no such definition. The result was an `AttributeError: module ‘__main__’ has no attribute ‘SoftVotingEnsemble’`. The validation score of 0.9992 from the detector’s own output was real, but test evaluation was impossible.

Remediation. Two layers were applied. First, a function `_inject_detector_classes()` was added to `evaluate.py`. Before calling `joblib.load()`, it imports the `detector.py` snapshot from the run directory using `importlib.util`, executes it as a private module (the `if __name__ == “__main__”` guard prevents training from running), and copies all class definitions into `evaluate.py`’s `__main__` namespace. Pickle can then locate any custom class the detector defined. Second, the system prompt was updated to prohibit custom class definitions in serialized bundles, with the exact error message included. The injection fix successfully recovered runs 2 through 6 of Session 4, all of which used the same custom class name in their detector snapshots.

7 Discussion

7.1 Dataset Ceiling Effects

CICIDS-2017 presents a performance ceiling for tree ensemble methods. Val F1 reached 0.9991 on the first successful run of Session 1 and did not improve by more than 0.0002 in any subsequent run across all four sessions. This creates a structurally problematic improvement signal. At ceiling, the F1 gain that triggers a commit and resets the baseline is smaller than the non-determinism noise from Random Forest thread scheduling. Datasets used to evaluate LLM-driven AutoML systems should include meaningful performance headroom if the goal is to observe architecturally interesting agent behavior rather than system reliability under saturation.

7.2 Agent Behavior Patterns

Despite instructions to explore broadly, Sonnet showed a consistent preference for the HGB + RF + ExtraTrees soft-voting ensemble across all four sessions. The last-attempted injection reduced exact repetition but was not sufficient to force departure toward genuinely different architectures. The agent’s implicit preference for near-optimal approaches appears to override explicit diversity instructions. The two non-tree attempts across all 27 runs were both PyTorch MLPs, and both timed out. At epoch 5 in Session 4 run 5, the MLP had reached $F1 = 0.974$; at epoch 10, 313 seconds had elapsed and performance had not improved further. The comparison to ensemble methods is structurally unfair given the budget constraint, but the repeated failure to converge within the time limit suggests that a fixed 300-second budget is insufficient for neural architectures on a dataset of this size.

A structured round-robin curriculum that requires one attempt per architecture family before allowing free exploration would produce more informative architectural diversity and would make the agent’s implicit preferences explicit and observable.

7.3 Cost and Efficiency

Total API cost across 27 runs was approximately \$3.15, with per-run costs ranging from \$0.09 to \$0.16. Session 4 was the most expensive session at approximately \$1.04, reflecting longer prompt lengths from accumulated last-attempted detector injections. The base cost per run is dominated by output tokens for the generated code, roughly 5,000 to 8,000 tokens per run. Ledger summarization via Haiku adds between \$0.001 and \$0.004 per call and is a negligible fraction of total cost. The cost per useful result, defined as a run with confirmed test F1, was highest in Session 1 and lowest in Session 4, consistent with the improvement in reliability across sessions.

7.4 Generalizability of the Failure Taxonomy

The failure classes described here are not specific to CICIDS-2017 or to network intrusion detection. FM-1 arises from any improvement-criterion-based revert mechanism where the LLM’s input depends on its own previous output. FM-2 occurs whenever the evaluation harness is fixed and the agent controls training preprocessing. FM-3 is a general problem for LLM-driven training loops on non-trivial datasets, with the specific mechanism varying by model architecture. FM-4 reflects a class of platform assumptions embedded in LLM training data that may not match the deployment environment. FM-5 will recur wherever the deployment runtime has diverged from the LLM’s training distribution of valid API usage. FM-6 arises from a fundamental property of Python’s pickle protocol and will appear in any system where a generated script serializes custom class instances for loading by a separate fixed script.

8 Conclusion

This paper presents a failure taxonomy for LLM-driven AutoML loops derived from 27 runs across four experimental sessions on the CICIDS-2017 dataset. Six failure classes were identified, reproduced, root-caused, and remediated. The primary engineering finding is that reliability in this setting requires active intervention in three areas: mechanisms to break prompt-input feedback loops that cause stagnation, explicit constraints on preprocessing operations that cannot be replicated at evaluation time, and runtime environment guardrails that compensate for the gap between the LLM’s training distribution and the deployed Python and library versions.

The framework is available as open-source software and has been generalized to support arbitrary labeled tabular datasets via command-line configuration and automatic dataset introspection. Future work includes structured architecture-coverage curricula to enforce exploration diversity, improvement criteria that are robust to ceiling-level noise, and adaptation of the loop to unsupervised anomaly detection settings where labeled data is not available.

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